

A kinetic and mechanistic study on the oxidation of indole-3-propionic acid by peroxomonosulphate in acetonitrile medium and biological activity of the product formed

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Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of indole-3-propionic acid by peroxomonosulphate has been carried out in aqueous acetonitrile medium. Reactions were carried out at four different temperatures (288, 293, 298 and 313 K). It was observed that the rate of the reaction increases with increase in temperature of the reaction mixture. First order dependence of rate with respect to [IPA] and [PMS] was noticed. Variation of ionic strength (μ) has negligible effect on reaction rate. Rate of the reaction was not influenced by the increase in the concentration of H^+ ion. Increase in the percentage of acetonitrile decreases the reaction rate. Absence of free radical was confirmed by adding acrylonitrile to the reaction mixture and no polymer formation was noticed. Product analysis was carried out and the main product has been identified by IR, NMR spectral studies. Based on these above facts a suitable ionic mechanism has been proposed and hence the corresponding rate equation was derived. The biological activity such as antibacterial and antifungal activity of the product was studied in ethanol medium. The reactivity of peroxomonosulphate over IPA was found to be lower in acetic acid medium than in acetonitrile medium. The thermodynamic parameters such as E_a , ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger were computed. The effect of catalyst on the rate of the reaction was also carried out. The final oxidised product was analysed for its corrosion inhibition property on mild steel in acid medium.

Keywords : Oxidation, IPA, peroxomonosulphate, acetonitrile, biological activity.

Introduction

Heterocyclic compounds with ring system are of special importance in life processes. Among these imidazole and indole are present in proteins, pyrimidine and purine are found in genes¹. Some indole derivatives like indole-3-acetic acid and IPA have great growth promoting action on plants and are known as heteroauxins or phyto hormones².

Peroxomonosulphate is a class of chemical compound which possess a unique property of participating in many chemical reactions. The high oxidation potential (1.82 V) suggests the feasibility of many room temperature oxidations with peroxomonosulphate³⁻¹¹. The synthetic utility of peroxomonosulphate with different kinds of organic substrate has been reported¹². Hence the study on the

oxidation of IPA by peroxomonosulphate is chosen which is of much biological and chemical significance.

Experimental

All the chemicals required are of AR grade E. Merck samples and are used as such. Doubly distilled water was employed in the preparation of aqueous solutions. In a typical experiment, appropriate amount of IPA, sulphuric acid, acrylonitrile and sodium bisulphate and water were taken in a reaction vessel and thermostated at the desired temperature. The temperature range selected was between 288–303 K. A measured amounts of oxidant peroxomonosulphate also thermostated at the same temperature. A required amount of oxidant was pipetted out into the reaction mixture and the liberated iodine was titrated against thio sulphate using starch as the indicator. The progress

of the reaction was monitored by iodometric determination of unreacted oxidant. The course of the reaction was followed for 75% of completion of the reaction. Plot of log [oxidant] vs time were made. The values of pseudo-first order rate constants k' obtained were reproducible within $\pm 5\%$.

The selected bacterial and fungal clinical isolates were obtained from Rath Diagnostic Laboratory, Tiruchirappalli and maintained in nutrient agar slants. The isolates used were *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterobacter* sp., *E. coli*, *Salmonella paratyphi*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Streptococci* sp. for testing antibacterial activity.

The antibacterial activity of synthesized product was evaluated by agar diffusion method using nutrient agar. The antifungal activity of the synthesized product was evaluated by agar diffusion method using potato dextrose agar. The zone of inhibition surrounding the well was measured and compared with control for both measurements.

The specimens for weight loss measurements were pre-treated by usual methods. Weight loss measurements were done by hanging steel plate in a glass beaker containing 100 mL of corrosive media (1.0 M H₂SO₄) without and with different concentration of inhibitor for an immersion time of 4 h. The steel plate was taken out and washed out with tap water followed by distilled water dried and weighed accurately using digital balance of accuracy ± 0.1 mg. Weight loss experiments were carried out at 40 °C in a digital controlled water bath (± 0.1 °C accuracy). All experiments were carried out in static and aerated condition. Each measurement was repeated thrice for reproducibility and an average value was reported. The η_w (percentage inhibition efficiency) was calculated from the following relationship.

$$\eta_w = \frac{w^0 - w}{w^0} \times 100$$

where w^0 and w are weight loss in the absence and presence of inhibitor.

Product analysis :

The reaction mixture containing a slight excess of peroxomonosulphate over the substrate with other addi-

tives maintained as in the regular kinetic runs was kept aside at room temperature for about 48 h, for completion of the reaction. Then the remaining reaction mixture was poured into doubly distilled water. A residual solid thus obtained was filtered washed and dried. The solid mass was characterised as a product by FT-IR and ¹H NMR spectral data.

Results and discussion

Dependence of reaction on oxidant and substrate :

The kinetic run was carried out with stoichiometric excess of substrate at constant peroxomonosulphate. Plots of log [PMS] vs time were linear with slope equal to unity. The value of pseudo-first order rate constant k' is given in Table 1. An increase in [IPA] has increased the pseudo-first order rate constant, thus indicating first order dependence on [IPA]. In order to determine the order of reaction with respect to the oxidant the reaction was carried out at different initial concentrations of oxidant and at fixed concentration of other reactants. The k' values are given in Table 1 and it is seen that the reaction is independent of PMS concentration. This clearly shows that the reaction is of first order with respect to the change in concentration of oxidant.

Table 1. Effect of change in concentration of oxidant on the reaction rate

[PMS] × 10 ² (mol/dm ³)	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0
$k' \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	12.52	12.36	12.52	12.46	12.39

Effect of ionic strength on the rate of reaction :

Ionic strength of the medium was varied by adding sodium bisulphate (mol dm⁻³). It was seen that the variation of ionic strength has no effect on the rate of the

Table 2. Variation of IPA

[PMS] = 2 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [H⁺] = 0.02 mol dm⁻³, μ = 0.3 mol dm⁻³, Acetonitrile = 50% v/v, T = 303 K

[IPA] × 10 ² (mol dm ⁻³)	$k' \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	$k_2 \times 10^2$ (mol dm ⁻³)
2.0	8.4827	4.2413
2.5	10.7473	4.2989
3.0	12.5513	4.1837
3.5	14.278	4.0794
4.0	17.0957	4.2989

reaction. This shows that the reaction takes place between a neutral molecule and a negative species.

Effect of temperature on the rate of the reaction :

The reaction was studied at different temperature in the range 288–303 K and the values of k' were determined from the pseudo-first order plot (Table 3). The energy of activation E_a was evaluated. The other activation parameters were calculated and are presented.

[IPA] $\times 10^2$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$k' \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)			
	288 K	293 K	298 K	303 K
2.0	2.3413	3.4928	5.7114	8.4827
2.5	2.9171	4.5369	6.9435	10.7473
3.0	3.5696	5.4619	8.2370	12.5513
3.5	4.2605	6.3217	9.8760	14.2780
4.0	4.6827	7.2813	11.0313	17.1957

Test for free radicals on the rate of the reaction :

The addition of acrylonitrile monomer solution into the reaction mixture did not initiate polymerization, indicating the absence of *in situ* formation of free radical species in the reaction sequence.

Effect of dielectric constant :

The solvent plays an important role by altering the rate. Acetonitrile is both a weaker base and weaker acid than water. Therefore in acetonitrile IPA will exist as neutral species. The reactions were carried out in aqueous acetonitrile medium with a dielectric constant (37.5) different from that of pure water (80). The effect of dielectric constant on the reaction rate by varying the percentage of acetonitrile in the reaction mixture (30–55 % v/v) was studied. The rate of the reaction was found to decrease with increase in the percentage of acetonitrile (i.e.) with decrease in dielectric constant of the reaction mixture. This indicates that there is a charge development in the transition state involving a more polar activated complex than the reactants¹³, a neutral molecule [IPA] and a negative ion (HSO_5^-) and absence of ion-ion or dipole-dipole type mechanism, which is also supported by the highly negative ΔS^\ddagger values obtained in this work (Table 4).

Mechanism :

Based on the above results the following ionic mechanism is proposed.

Table 4. Rate and activation parameters

E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	61.72
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	59.28
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-75.86
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	82.29
log A	11.26

The reaction proceeds through an electrophilic attack of the oxidant (peroxomonosulphate) at the nucleophilic site C3 of indole-3-propionic acid by a mechanism involving nucleophilic displacement of sulphate ion to form 3-hydroxy-indole-3-propionic acid intermediate (indolenine intermediate) as the rate determining step¹⁴. This intermediate undergoes intramolecular rearrangement to give 2-hydroxy indole-3-propionic acid through a cyclic intermediate. The second attack of peroxomonosulphate ion on 2-hydroxy-indole-3-propionic acid gives 2,3-dihydroxy-indole-3-propionic acid which undergoes lactonisation to give 2-hydroxy- γ -spirolactone indolenine intermediate^{15–18}. The intermediate which then loses H^+ to give namely γ -spirolactone oxindole as the product.

Weight loss measurements :

The oxidised product of IPA (γ -spirolactone) shows more corrosion inhibition effect than the substrate (IPA) at all concentrations as shown in Table 5. It was very clear that the substrate and the product inhibits the corrosion of mild steel in 1 M H₂SO₄ solution at all concentration was used in this study and the corrosion rate (C_R) decreases continuously with increasing additive concentration at 313 K. The presence of electron releasing character of OH group may be attributed to the increased electron density leading to electron transfer mechanism from the functional group to the metal surface also larger molecular size can be considered which ensures greater coverage of the metallic surface¹⁹⁻²¹.

Table 5. Inhibition efficiency of IPA and its oxidised product in 1 M H₂SO₄

Sr. no.	Compound	Values of inhibition efficiency (%) for different concentrations (M) of inhibitors		
		0.1 M	0.01 M	0.001 M
1.	Substrate	62.50	18.75	6.25
2.	Product	68.42	63.15	42.10

Biological activity :

The product γ -spirolactone oxindole showed inhibitory activity against the bacterial pathogen *Pseudomonas* sp. and *Proteus* sp. The zone of inhibition increased on increasing the concentration. It fails to show the inhibitory activity against other pathogens like *Streptococcus* sp. and *Salmonella paratyphi* etc. The product γ -spirolactone shows significant antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*.

Table 6. Antifungal activity of the product γ -spirolactone oxindole

Sr. no.	Name of the fungal pathogen	Zone of inhibition at different concentration of γ -spirolactone oxindole (mm)				
		100	200	300	400	500
		$\mu\text{g/mL}$	$\mu\text{g/mL}$	$\mu\text{g/mL}$	$\mu\text{g/mL}$	$\mu\text{g/mL}$
1.	<i>Candida albicans</i>	-	2	3	5	6
2.	Amphoterician B	-	-	-	-	15

(-) Absence of activity.

Conclusion

Thus IPA-PMS system undergoes reaction through ionic mechanism. Both the substrate and the product shows

maximum corrosion inhibition activity towards mild steel. The oxidised product act as a good antifungal and antibacterial agent. The oxidised solid mass was characterised as a product by FT-IR and ¹H NMR spectral data.

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